

FATIGUE OF FIBRE COMPOSITES FOR WIND TURBINE ROTOR BLADES

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ABSTRACT: The present paper describes a test programme to investigate (alternative) fatigue formulations. Their background and the possibilities to solve the problem of predicting the lifetime and residual strength under variable amplitude loading accurately and reliably are described. Most composite fatigue research to date has focussed on semi-empirical damage accumulation- or residual strength degradation models. The validation of these models requires a large and consistent experimental effort. This effort is usually frustrated by the large scatter in fatigue results on composite materials and the great variety in material systems. The present paper describes the test programme and means of dealing with this scatter.

KEYWORDS: composite fatigue, wind turbine blades, variable amplitude, test programme description

COMPOSITES IN WIND TURBINE ROTOR BLADES

For composites in general, and particularly for wind turbine rotor blade composites, current developments are most urgent are in the fields of cost reduction and lifetime prediction [1]. For wind turbine rotor blades, a relatively low ratio of cost versus reliability is an important requirement. The price of wind power in a liberalised market can only be competitive if turbine price and operation and maintenance cost are low. This means that composites for blades must be cost-effectively produced. Rotor blade materials are therefore usually not 'aerospace-grade' composites, although, through the advent of vacuum assisted production methods, the quality of the wind turbine composites has improved (lower void content).

High reliability means that accurate and reliable lifetime prediction methods or residual strength prediction methods must be available.

Maintenance- and (automated) condition monitoring techniques for rotor blades are currently under development, but the need for repair should be avoided if possible.

Properties of materials typical for wind turbine rotor blade applications can be found in [2, 3]. An overview including relevant references to general wind turbine composite fatigue research is presented in a related paper on this conference [4].

Figure 1: Fatigue of composites in wind turbine blades

VARIABLE AMPLITUDE FATIGUE IN COMPOSITES

Although many composite structures are considered fatigue insensitive, extensive research has been conducted in this field, especially for applications which sustain a high number of varying load cycles during their lifetime. Driven by use of composites in aerospace applications, life prediction under random fatigue loads has been a subject of investigation since the 1970s [5, 6]. Research has focussed

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on predicting life of composites, predicting residual strength or -stiffness (-degradation), or relating physically observable damage (e.g. crack density) to the expected life of a composite.

Reifsnider [7] discusses micromechanical aspects of fatigue damage accumulation in mainly uni-directional and carbon fibre reinforced composites. Fatigue mechanisms have recently been evaluated by Gamstedt [8]. Yang and co-workers devised strength- and stiffness degradation models, which account for non-linear damage accumulation, e.g. [9, 10]. Recent work on spectral load fatigue is found in [11, 12, 13]. An overview of fatigue research specifically focussing on fatigue of wind turbine composites can be found in [14 - 17].

The most important problem with validating the resulting plethora of lifetime prediction-, residual strength-, and stiffness degradation models is lack of testing time. In part, this is caused by the generally large scatter in lifetime to failure of composite materials. Also, the variation in materials and testing geometries is large, which means that results of different types of tests may not be easily correlated.

However, there are other aspects related to developing and validating a lifetime prediction model or residual strength prediction model which may significantly influence lifetime estimates. There are several necessary ingredients in a lifetime prediction of composite materials. The following discusses these steps and their relationships. A test programme for validating composite fatigue models is discussed at the end of this paper.

(Rainflow) counting method

A load cycle count algorithm is part of any fatigue analysis. For spectral loads, different methods exist for characterizing the fatigue cycles in the signal. These can be level crossing methods, peak count methods, range counting methods, etc. Which cycle characteristics are counted (amplitude only or a combination of mean and amplitude) depends on the model for which the cycle count results are an input. Commonly, a combination of amplitude and mean, or equivalent characteristics, is required. Classically, the rainflow counting method is regarded as the most appropriate method for evaluating the load characteristics of a spectral load. Generally, no account is taken of the frequency.

The rainflow method was simultaneously developed by Endo et al. and de Jonge [18, 19]. Similar counting methods and associated hard- and software for field data acquisition were developed by [20, 21], specifically for the automotive industry. Ultimately, two different basic algorithms, which are *both* referred to as rainflow counting, exist. The method developed by Endo et al./ de Jonge, starts and ends at an arbitrary point in the signal. Cycles are extracted via the Rainflow algorithm described in figure 2. Not all cycles are extracted directly. When the final peak is encountered, a residual of peaks and troughs remains and this sequence can be counted as half cycles. Thus, the result is expressed in terms of half cycles.

The other algorithm, by Downing [21], counts a signal as if it were rearranged to start and end with the maximum peak or minimum trough. This means that no half cycles are counted.

Some variations on the two above main themes are occasionally encountered in the literature, but mostly, use is made of the two described methods. In most relevant guidelines for fatigue analysis of wind turbines, the Endo/de Jonge method is used [22, 23].

It must be noted that, if the load signal is rearranged to start and end with the maximum peak or minimum trough, the counting results from both methods are identical. Which method is used should be clearly stated since the lifetime prediction result can be considerably influenced by the counting method.

Figure 2: Description of Rainflow count (top), cyclic Rainflow count, and range count

S-N curve interpolation in the S-N diagram

Another important issue is interpolation of fatigue data in an S-N diagram, which has S (generic term representing stress component of the fatigue load) on the ordinate and N (generic term describing number of cycles to failure) on the abscissa. Constant amplitude S-N diagrams are used as a basis for lifetime prediction in variable amplitude load situations. To find the mean of the expected lifetime for a constant amplitude load, simple linear regression may suffice (note that although S is usually on the ordinate, it is actually the independent variable in regression analyses). As a model for the fit, either an exponential or power law representation of the S-N curve may be assumed:

Figure 3: Exponential and power law S-N curve

$$\log(N) = a + b \cdot \sigma_{amp} \quad (\text{exponential}) \quad (1)$$

$$\log(N) = c + d \cdot \log(\sigma_{amp}), \text{ or, equivalently: } N = 10^c \cdot \sigma_{amp}^d \quad (\text{power law}) \quad (2)$$

See figure 3 for an example. Generally, research has converged on the thesis that the power law expression is the more valid, especially for high cycle fatigue. However, lifetime prediction results are very sensitive to the choice of model, especially in the high-cycle regime ($N > 10^6$) [16, 24].

S-N-curves and tolerance bounds

For design, lower tolerance bounds, or lower confidence bounds, need to be derived from S-N curves, describing the value of lifetime above which $p\%$ of any future tests will lie with $\gamma\%$ confidence (note that lifetime is always the dependent variable in an S-N diagram notwithstanding the fact that it is often plotted on the abscissa). Calculation of tolerance bounds depends on the nature of the statistical distribution of fatigue data. Usually, the data are assumed to be Normal distributed with standard deviation σ and mean μ . If the standard deviation is assumed constant along a range of fatigue lives, the mean at each stress level can be determined using linear regression in combination with eq. 1 or 2. In this case, the lower tolerance limit is defined as:

Figure 4: Schematic of S-N curve and associated statistics

$$T_{lower} = \mu - c_{n,p,\gamma} \cdot \sigma \quad (3)$$

where $c_{n,p,\gamma}$ is tabulated for frequently occurring combinations of number of data points n , p and γ [e.g. 25].

Whitney and Sendekyj [26, 27] have proposed methods which allow the characterization of the fatigue data using a Weibull distribution. These methods involve finding the Weibull-parameters via an iterative maximum likelihood scheme. Through the use of a data pooling system, data from several stress or strain levels can be used to find a constant Weibull distribution along the data range, and run-outs (fatigue tests which have been terminated prior to failure) can be included, see also [28]. Whitney uses a power law S-N-curve to interpolate S-N data, whereas Sendekyj includes a strength degradation model in his method and an additional iterative scheme to obtain the relevant model parameters. Sendekyj's method thus allows for description of data over a wider range of lifetimes, including the low-cycle regime (lifetimes $<10^3$).

When only the mean expected lifetimes are to be compared between lifetime prediction models, a linear regression usually suffices to characterize lifetime.

S-N curve interpolation in the Constant Life Diagram

A constant life diagram (CLD) depicts the relationship between mean expected fatigue life and a combination of stress- or strain amplitude and –mean. Sometimes, tolerance bounds are used as a basis for the CLD. The CLD is closely related to the S-N diagram. This relationship is depicted in figure 5.

Since the work load associated with describing the entire CLD experimentally is enormous, interpolation has to be used. The linear Goodman interpolation is not generally valid for fiber reinforced composites. Linear interpolation between R-values for which experimental data are available is most commonly used. As a fatigue calculation is highly sensitive to the type of interpolation method chosen, as shown in e.g. (Kensche in [14], 29, 30), and since the 'best' interpolation method for composites has not been found yet it is important to obtain test results on the relevant material for a sufficiently fine grid of R-values. Part of the work of Mandell and co-workers is aimed at this [16].

Figure 5: Relation between SN-curve and constant life diagram

Spectrum load lifetime prediction

Once the constant amplitude behaviour of a composite is quantified, a formulation is necessary to use this information to assess the estimated lifetime in irregular cyclic loads. Classically, this is done through the well-known Miner summation, where fracture is assumed to occur at a damage number D equal to 1:

$$D = \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{n_i}{N_i} = 1 \quad (4)$$

where each cycle of type i (characterized by minimum and maximum value) contributes to the damage number by comparing the number of occurrences with the number of occurrences that would be expected in a strictly constant amplitude load, N_i . The value of N_i is taken from figure 5.

Although D is frequently indicated as the damage number, it does not account for any physical accumulation of damage. It cannot be asserted that D represents the fraction of total damage at any given fraction of lifetime. As a result, the contribution to D of different cycle types is independent of the order in which they occur, and D only has physical meaning if its value is equal to or larger than 1 (i.e., failure has occurred). For any other value less than 1, D merely designates 'no fracture'. Adding (non-linear) parameters to the Miner's sum to force the value at failure to 1 for specific experimental

results, or the use of Miner's sums less than one for engineering purposes, as proposed by [31], does not eliminate this widely recognized deficiency of eq. 4.

A method which does take into account the load history, is the class of residual strength degradation models. As the name suggests, these formulations have the added advantage of quantifying residual strength at any life fraction in a constant amplitude load sequence. The general form is (see also figure 6):

$$X_r = UTS - (UTS - \sigma_{max}) \cdot \left(\frac{n_{eq} + n_i}{N_i} \right)^C \quad (5)$$

where X_r is the residual strength, UTS is Ultimate Tensile Strength (this particular model refers to tensile dominated failure), σ_{max} is maximum occurring strength in a constant amplitude signal, n/N is lifetime fraction and C is an exponent determining the nature of the strength degradation. This parameter has to be determined from residual strength tests. This expression has been developed and used by several authors as a (part of) a model for lifetime prediction [e.g. 9, 12].

In a spectral load lifetime prediction, the way this expression is used is as follows. Starting at X_r equal to the initial strength, cycles are counted until the type of cycle changes (in terms of amplitude or mean). The residual strength at the end of this first section is calculated via eq. 5. Then, for the next section of a single cycle type, the number of cycles is calculated which would have been necessary to arrive at this value of X_r . This is the equivalent number of cycles n_{eq} . Next, the residual strength at the end of the second section is calculated, the equivalent number of cycles with the characteristics of the third section is calculated and this is repeated until the end of the sequence is encountered.

Figure 6: Residual strength degradation model

The most illustrative example of a spectral load to validate this model is a two-block test. This is a test which consists of two types of constant amplitude blocks, where the first block is a fixed fraction of the expected lifetime, and the second block is continued until final fracture occurs. Typically, Miner's sum at fracture is not equal to 1 for this type of tests. Usually, values for Miner's sum greater than 1 are encountered in High-Low test results (where the amplitude of the first block is greater than that of the second block) and less than 1 for Low-High tests.

Figure 7: Predicted Miner's sums at failure for residual strength degradation in two-block tests

In figure 7, the predicted Miner sums at failure are depicted dependent on parameters of the residual strength degradation model and of the parameters of the two-block test. As can be seen, eq. 5 leads to Miner sums greater than 1 for High-Low tests and less than one for Low-High block tests, a trend which is also observed in the scarce data available in the literature (e.g. [6], Bonnee in [14]). Note that, if the sequence starts with a low-amplitude block, and the value of C is small (i.e. a major part of the strength degradation occurs in an early stage), the maximum stress at the start of the second block may be too high, and fracture occurs at the start of the second block. This is schematically indicated by the hatched area in figure 7.

Two potential problems can be identified with this model. First, application of the model in an all-tensile or all-compressive load spectrum is straightforward. For each block of tests either the tensile- or the compressive residual strength degradation is monitored and input into the next block. However, if both tensile and compressive loads occur, for each block both tensile and compressive strength degradation may have to be quantified. How the interaction between compressive and tensile residual strength degradation and transition between blocks should be handled is unclear.

Also, the use of strength degradation models complicates the use of the Rainflow cycle counting method. Going from a peak to the next trough or vice versa involves performing a Rainflow count on the signal including and excluding the last peak or trough and analyzing the differences. Not only does this mean a considerable computational effort, by nature of the counting algorithm, the difference may be in multiple cycle types. Therefore, it is most practical to resort to the method of considering each new peak or trough as a half cycle, i.e. performing a range count. Computational effort is low and the result is unambiguous. However, care should be taken when comparing results using a range count with results from other models employing a Rainflow count.

VARIABLE AMPLITUDE AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH TEST PROGRAMME

As is described in the previous sections, many uncertainties accumulate in the set-up of a lifetime prediction for composites. Experimental work is necessary to mitigate some of these uncertainties. The strength degradation formulation should be validated, the associated value(s) for the strength degradation parameter(s) should be found, and the resulting lifetime predictions should be confirmed for both simple and more complex spectral loads. An interconsistent test programme has been defined, which will be described in this chapter. Test results are expected to become available in the course of the coming year, as part of the work in the Task Groups 1 and 5 concerned with variable amplitude loading and residual strength degradation in the OPTIMAT project.

The main features of the test programme are the use of a single specimen geometry for a large variety of tests, and the definition of standard stress levels to mitigate interpolation influences in developing and validating the variable amplitude models.

As is pointed out in [4], a single specimen geometry has been defined to facilitate the correlation of different test types. The variable amplitude programme aims to find life prediction methods for specimens loaded in both tensile and compressive modes, and it is linked to the residual strength programme which features both fatigue and static tests. Static compression, tensile and fatigue tests at various R-ratios should be easily compared. Now, this comparison is not obscured by geometrical differences.

In addition, a limited number of stress levels was defined. Three test levels are defined per R-ratio, based on the expected number of cycles to failure. To minimize testing time, the stress levels are standardized to 10^3 , $5 \cdot 10^4$ and 10^6 cycles. Although wind turbines experience 10^8 to 10^9 number of cycles during their lifetime, this was deemed to be the best compromise between amount of tests and testing time.

Constant amplitude tests for S-N characterization are concentrated on these levels. Also, variable amplitude tests and residual strength tests occur only on (combinations of) these predefined levels. In order to obtain these levels, a preliminary test programme was carried out.

The test programme consists of roughly two parts: a collection of tests which serves the purpose of establishing the residual strength degradation of the material, and a series of tests subjecting the material to a range of variable amplitude loading spectra in order to validate the residual strength degradation theory.

figure 8: Schematic of foreseen S-N characterization tests. Closed dots indicate combination of R-value and lifetime for which both constant amplitude- and residual strength tests will be performed (open dots S-N characterization only; numbers indicate standardized stress levels; arrows indicate possible two-block test combinations.

Basic S-N characterization (constant amplitude fatigue tests) is the fundament of the spectrum fatigue investigation. As explained above, the focus is on the predefined stress levels. In total, a number of approx. 150 constant amplitude tests are foreseen, distributed over ca. 7 R-ratios, with emphasis on the R-ratios -1 (tension-compression), 10 (compression-compression) and 0.1 (tension-tension). The S-N-curve characterization grid is schematically displayed in the σ_{mean} - σ_{amp} -plane in figure 8. The exact location of the tests is not defined in this figure.

Residual strength tests are performed at selected fractions of the expected lifetime. In figure 8, these tests are indicated by closed dots. In figure 9, the residual strength tests are further elaborated. The test is aimed at finding the residual strength after

fatigue of a specimen. The specimen is subjected to a fatigue load corresponding to one of the predefined stress levels. After the predefined fraction of lifetime has been reached, the fatigue loading is stopped and the specimen undergoes a static test. This is either a compressive or a tensile test. To obtain statistically viable test results, a number of residual strength tests has to be performed at each combination of stress level and life fraction. In this programme, the number of tests has been set to a minimum of 4 tensile and 4 compressive tests. Even though the number of specimens has been kept to this minimum, performing a complete set of residual strength tests on one 'dot' in figure 8 amounts to $(8 \cdot 0.2 + 8 \cdot 0.5 + 8 \cdot 0.8) = 12$ times the number of cycles necessary to load a specimen to the expected number of cycles for that stress level.

In addition, ca. 150 two-block tests and repeated two-block tests are foreseen. In the two-block tests, the first block continues until 50% of the expected lifetime, the second block is continued until failure. In the repeated block tests, a sequence of two shorter blocks (1% of expected lifetime) is repeated until failure. Testing a larger number of different blocks was discarded because the possible

Figure 9: Overview of consistent tests per R-value (ratio of minimum and maximum stress)

number of block-combinations is already extensive, as is clear from figure 8. The block tests serve mainly as a validation of the residual strength tests. Therefore, from all possible block stress level combinations, only those combinations are chosen for which residual strength tests have been performed. Generally there is a lack of test results involving blocks with both compressive and tensile components. In figure 8, a selection of possible block combinations is indicated with dotted lines. The exact combinations of stress levels and R-ratio that will be performed depends on the location of the S-N curves and available testing time. Interesting combinations are High-Low, Low-High

combinations (levels 1, 3) for $R=-1$, 10 and 0.1, to investigate sequence effects for the material. Also of interest are tests with alternating tension-tension and compression-compression cycles (i.e. each block has different R -value), as recommended e.g. by Wahl [17], who has performed numerous repeated two-block tests, where each block constituted a small fraction of the lifetime. From these results and from results on more complicated spectra in the tensile regime he concludes that Miner's sum at fracture is not dependent on sequence, and that simple

prediction methodologies such as suggested

by Echtermeyer et al. [31] may suffice for engineering purposes. However, the inaccuracy of lifetime prediction methods may in part be contributed to inaccurate estimation of the damage growth due to occasional excursions into the compression region.

Finally, several tests are devoted to more complicated spectra, which will also be used to validate the residual strength degradation models, such as the standardized loading spectrum for wind turbine blade materials WISPER and new variants. An impression of the WISPER spectrum is seen in figure 10. This spectrum consists of 132,000 cycles, mainly in the tensile stress regime. As can be seen, there are a few excursions into the compression region and one large tensile peak. Variants of WISPER are WISPERX (a shortened version by omission of small amplitude cycles) and RWISPER (Reversed WISPER with predominantly compressive loads). For details on WISPER, refer to [32].

Figure 10 WISPER load sequence

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The *building* blocks of a fatigue calculation and alternative formulations were discussed. A dedicated test programme to corroborate the choice of an appropriate fatigue calculation method has been detailed. The focus of this large and consistent experimental programme is on the development and validation of semi-empirical residual strength degradation models. The test programme comprises a multitude of basic S-N characterization tests, residual strength degradation tests, and spectrum tests varying from two-block tests to WISPER- and related variable amplitude tests. Influences of the choice of S-N interpolation methods were mitigated by the use of standardized stress levels which correspond to fixed estimated lifetimes. Influences of test geometry were minimized by standardizing the specimen geometry for all tests. Test results are expected to become available in the next year.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Part of this work was carried out under auspices of the OPTIMAT blades project, funded by the European Committee under contract number ENK6-CT-2001-00552, see also [33].

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